

Understanding Lifestyle Marketing Mix (LISA) Impacts On Brand Equity And Customer Equity In Beauty Services Industries: Evidence From Jakarta, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

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This study examines how lifestyle-oriented marketing complements the traditional service marketing mix in shaping brand equity and customer equity in high-involvement service contexts. It investigates the relative and combined effects of the service marketing mix (SERV) and lifestyle marketing mix (LISI) on brand equity and customer equity in Jakarta's premium beauty services industry. Using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with survey data from 200 premium salon customers, results show that both SERV and LISI significantly and positively affect brand equity, with lifestyle elements demonstrating stronger influence than traditional service components. Brand equity fully mediates the relationship between the integrated SERVLISI mix and customer equity. The study reconceptualizes lifestyle as an operable marketing mix component, demonstrating that brand equity formation in lifestyle-driven service settings depends more on lifestyle congruence than service performance alone. Businesses are recommended to integrate lifestyle-oriented strategies alongside traditional service quality measures to maximize brand equity and customer loyalty.

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Introduction

The global fashion and beauty industry has undergone a profound transformation over the past decade, shifting from product-centric consumption toward experience, identity, and lifestyle-driven value creation. In the post-pandemic period, particularly, fashion and beauty brands and service businesses increasingly compete not only on quality but on their capacity to resonate with consumers' self-concepts, emotional fulfillment, and symbolic expression (Pangarkar et al., 2021). This transformation has been further accelerated by a growing consumer emphasis on self-care, well-being, and personal identity, particularly within premium and experiential market segments. As consumers reassessed their personal values and lifestyles, demand increasingly favored brands and services that align with individual identity, emotional reassurance, and long-term well-being over short-term utilitarian benefits (Park et al., 2022). Within the beauty services sector, this transition has blurred the boundaries between wellness and lifestyle consumption, repositioning beauty services such as salons and personal care providers not merely as service establishments, but as experiential spaces in which brand identity is constructed and where customer identity formation and emotional recovery take place. Across both developed and emerging markets, lifestyle alignment has become a central determinant of brand differentiation and equity, reflecting a broader movement away from standardized marketing approaches toward more personalized and lifestyle-congruent strategies (Widjaja, 2016; Pangarkar et al., 2021). Consequently, service firms operating within

As one of the largest emerging economies in Southeast Asia, Indonesia has experienced sustained expansion of its urban middle class, accompanied by rising discretionary spending on fashion, beauty, and personal care services (Che Ngah, 2017; Lukihardianti & Yulianto, 2021). Historically, beauty services in Indonesia have evolved through four successive eras since 1970, namely the pioneer era, the fashion era, the lifestyle era, and the modern lifestyle era (Widjaja, 2006). Although the beauty services industry, including the salon sector, has consistently sought to remain responsive to emerging trends, it has rarely sustained a position of market leadership across multiple eras. Prior to the pandemic, Widjaja (2016) documented that despite this ongoing evolution, many beauty salons continued to struggle with long-term sustainability, suggesting a fundamental misalignment between conventional service marketing mix strategies and contemporary consumer expectations. This inability to adequately respond to shifting consumer demand has progressively widened the customer value gap, one that the marketing mix, as currently conceptualized, has proven insufficient to address. The post-pandemic period has further compounded these challenges. Rather than reverting to pre-pandemic behavioral patterns, consumers have increasingly prioritized brands and services that align with their personal lifestyles and values, thereby elevating the strategic significance of lifestyle-oriented marketing approaches (Mecadinisa, 2021).

Taken together, Indonesia represents a particularly suitable empirical setting for examining lifestyle-oriented marketing strategies in the beauty services industry, with a specific focus on the salon sector. Its rapid economic growth, distinctive demographic structure, and accelerated lifestyle transformation collectively provide a theoretically appropriate and contextually rich environment for investigating the integration of lifestyle marketing mix dimensions into service marketing frameworks, an area that existing literature has yet to fully address. This study therefore, seeks to fill this gap by addressing the following research question: “How does the traditional service marketing mix influence brand equity in the premium beauty salon industry in Indonesia?”. The findings are expected to contribute to both theoretical and empirical literature by proposing a new conceptual model that serves as an alternative marketing strategy specifically tailored to the beauty services industry and which aligned with contemporary market conditions.

This study is organized into five sections. The first section examines how shifting consumer lifestyles have shaped beauty industry trends and establishes the significance of understanding this phenomenon. The second section presents a review of the relevant literature, along with a conceptual framework and discussion of prior studies related to the service marketing mix. The third section outlines the research methodology, including the data sources and analytical tools employed. The fourth section discusses the findings and key insights concerning the role of the lifestyle marketing mix as an alternative marketing strategy in the Indonesian beauty services industry. The final section offers concluding remarks and directions for future research.

Literature Review

The beauty services industry often occupies a distinctive position among personal services due to their high visibility and intimate association with physical appearance and emotional well-being. Unlike many utilitarian services, beauty services are repeatedly consumed in social contexts where outcomes are observable and subject to social evaluation. As a result, consumers place heightened emphasis on symbolic benefits, emotional resonance, and alignment with personal values when selecting service providers (Loureiro et al., 2013). These characteristics amplify the relevance of lifestyle congruence, the perceived match between a service brand and a consumer’s lifestyle orientation, as a critical evaluative criterion. Contemporary service consumption increasingly extends beyond functional utility toward symbolic and self-expressive value. Thus, the industry becomes a symbolic consumption, posits that consumers use products and services not only to satisfy practical needs but also to communicate identity, reinforce self-concept, and signal social belonging. In high-contact services, such as beauty salons, the service encounter itself becomes a medium through which consumers construct and project lifestyle narratives (Schiffman & Wisenblit, 2019). In this regard, service environments become desired not only as a modern lifestyle but shifted to a daily lifestyle that reflects consumers desired ways of living can foster deeper psychological engagement and long-term relational outcomes, as argued by Pangarkar et al. (2021). Given that purchase decision processes are shaped by consumers' personal characteristics, evaluative judgments, and external environmental stimuli, marketing activity can borrow the fundamental concept of consumer

demand towards the beauty services industry to construct the marketing mix, which represents one of the most fundamental concepts underpinning effective marketing strategy for both products and services (Azzadina et al., 2012). This way of thinking, highlighted by Wirtz (2020), marketing activity is an applied science that has borrowed significantly from basic fields, i.e., economics and psychology. The importance of marketing mix strategies is also not an exception to be applied in the beauty services industry. The inherently intangible nature of the beauty services industry presents both as an opportunity and a challenge to establish the business competitive advantage, as it directly influences the quality of service experienced by consumers and their ability to have their needs met. The marketing mix plays a critical role in maximizing service productivity and enhancing customer satisfaction, extending beyond the traditional elements of product, price, place, and promotion to encompass the full service encounter, from initial contact through the service process to post-service support, as well as the creation of tangible physical evidence (Wirtz & Lovelock, 2016). The strategic value of this approach has been empirically demonstrated by Heidari (2017), which confirming its positive impact on firm profitability and market share; and Mukherjee and Shivani (2016) study, establishing that service performance significantly influences both brand equity and customer equity. Accordingly, the adoption of a service-specific marketing mix is considered essential to enhancing overall service performance (Parmer et al., 2021).

Prior literature on the marketing mix have consistently identified lifestyle as a key psychological factor in consumers' economic decision-making (Joseph & Singh, 2013; Widjaja, 2016; Wirtz, 2020). Boonpradub and Thechatakerng (2015) define lifestyle as an individual's pattern of living, as expressed through activities, interests, and opinions formed through interaction with the surrounding environment. Lifestyle-driven needs can be categorized into four discretionary purchase types, namely extravagant, emotional, practical or necessity-based, and physical or material purchases (Danziger, 2006). This framework, grounded in individual characteristics rather than routine-based lifestyle classifications, is more analytically suited to examining consumer motivation and demand within the beauty services industry (Lamb et al., 2019). Consumer motivations and shopping patterns are closely integrated with behavioral tendencies and reflect consistent responses to environmental stimuli, which in turn drive shifting trends and evolving consumer demand (Schiffman & Wisenblit, 2019).

From a financial perspective, marketing strategies must be designed to attract new customers, cultivate strong customer relationships, retain existing clientele, and build sustainable business partnerships. The responsible management of customer information is a critical dimension of relationship quality and will increasingly determine the long-term strength of customer relationships (Li et al., 2023). These efforts collectively contribute to customer loyalty and equity, which serve as primary sources of competitive advantage rooted in brand equity (Wirtz & Lovelock, 2016). Brand equity is understood as the long-term outcome of sustained marketing mix performance, whereby higher levels of strategic effectiveness correspond to greater brand equity accumulation (Yoo et al., 2000).

From a customer-based perspective, brand equity encompasses the dimensions of performance, value, social image, trustworthiness, and commitment (Lassar et al., 1995), to which Tjiptono et al. (2004) subsequently added an attachment dimension. For brand equity to be effectively cultivated, consumers must be positioned to perceive and appreciate the brand at its intended value. By consistently generating added value through products and services, firms can foster greater customer loyalty, enhance resilience to price fluctuations and economic shocks, and build more sustainable competitive positions (Ballester & Munuera-Aleman, 2001; Beerli et al., 2004; Furrer, 2002). In this regard, marketers may strategically pursue lifestyle-targeted branding to deepen consumer alignment. Engaging service environments with emotional and interpersonal factors e.g., personalised services, price, place atmosphere, promotion, product, self-concept, and admiration in the form of brand equity, and service activity can supportively enhance emotional resonance and strengthen consumers' psychological bonds with service brands (Wirtz & Lovelock, 2016). These effects underscore the need for marketing frameworks that move beyond operational performance toward emotionally and lifestyle-responsive strategies. Over the long term, such marketing and branding efforts contribute to the development of brand equity as a significant financial asset, driving revenue growth and enhancing overall firm value (Aaker, 1991; Onditi, 2013; Pangarkar et al., 2021).

Hypothesis Development

Figure 2. Research Conceptual Models

Source: Processed Data (2025)

The hypotheses and conceptual framework of this research are constructed based various literature and the interaction process-based approach as shown in Figure 2. The first objective of this research is to prove the relationship between service mix (SERV) and lifestyle mix (LIST) impact on brand equity (BRAND) in long-term business sustainability. The second objective of this research is to prove brand equity (BRAND) impact on customer equity (EQUITY) using the SERV and LIST variables. For the third objective, the researcher measures the impact of brand equity (BRAND) on customer equity (EQUITY). This research also measures the degree of impact of SERV and LIST on BRAND, both directly and indirectly.

Service marketing mix (SERV) and brand equity (BRAND)

In services marketing, marketing performance is a result of service marketing mix which are the 7 Ps as follows product (service), price, place, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence. The 7 Ps strongly influencing on customer satisfaction, service performance and productivity, business competitive advantage. Furthermore, service performance has a significant impact to enhances brand image and brand equity (Choudhary, 2009; Keller, 2010; Kotler & Keller, 2016; Mukherjee & Shivani, 2016; Parmer et al., 2021; Tjiptono et al., 2004; Zeithaml et al., 2013)

H1: The impact of service marketing mix (SERV) on the brand equity (BRAND)

Lifestyle marketing mix (LIST) and brand equity (BRAND)

Nowadays consumers are more demanding and emotional to obtain intangible benefit. The current marketing mix was need to benefits from products or services that directly affecting brand status and image in market. Improving the performzance of the marketing mix will increase brand equity (Abd Aziz & Mohd Yasin, 2010; Keller, 2010; Kotler & Keller, 2016).

H2: The impact of lifestyle marketing mix (LIST) on the brand equity (BRAND)

Brand equity (BRAND) and customer equity (EQUITY)

Customer equity can be formed from the dimensions of value equity, brand equity, and relationship equity. The performance of marketing mix will increase value equity, brand equity, and customer relationship equity. Additionally, customer equity is the result of long-tern brand equity which can only occur if the customer presents significantly high loyalty (ultimate loyalty) that is formed from the accumulation of ultimate customer value, trustworthiness, attachment, and commitment. In conclusion, the relationship of brand equity to customer equity will improve financial performance and business sustainability, and loyal

customers that will generate stable business income (Delgado-Ballester & Munuera-Alemán, 2005; Kang et al., 2007; Kim et al., 2012; Ko et al., 2009).

H3: The impact of brand equity (BRAND) on the customer equity (EQUITY)

Method

This study was done descriptive-quantitatively using explanatory research with SEM (Structural Equation Modelling) method to verify the hypothesis. The data used in this research is primary data collected using a questionnaire method that is classified as a one-shot time horizon with the cross-section data type. The population in this study are beauty services industry customers in Indonesia that classifies as an open and unbounded population. To enhance representativeness and reduce sampling bias, a stratified random sampling technique was employed. The sample selected for this research as the benchmark is 200 beauty services customers of premium-level beauty salons in Jakarta from January to March 2025. The unit of analysis is the individual, who are the customers of premium level beauty salons in Jakarta. The number of representative samples for the use of the structural equation model referring to the provisions of Ghozali (2017) is around 100-200 samples.

All constructs were operationalized using multi-item scales adapted from established marketing and service literature and measured on a Likert-type scale. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was performed using the LISREL software package to simultaneously assess the measurement model and the structural relationships among constructs. SEM was selected due to its ability to estimate complex causal relationships involving latent variables while accounting for measurement error. This method of collecting data acknowledges the possibility of sampling and response bias that may occurs in this study. To reduce such a possibility and enhance the credibility of the findings, several procedural steps is implemented. First, to reduce sampling bias, stratified random sampling was employed rather than convenience sampling. By ensuring proportional representation across key customer segments, the study minimizes overrepresentation of any single demographic or behavioral group.

Second, response bias was mitigated by collecting data across multiple salon locations and time periods, thereby reducing location-specific or temporal effects. Participation was voluntary, and no material incentives were provided that could influence response patterns. Finally, this study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles governing human subjects research, adhering to the Indonesian regulatory framework stipulated in the National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN) Regulation Number 22 of 2022 concerning Research Ethics Clearance. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to completing the questionnaire. Thus, thee data collection process and analysis was designed to prioritize respondent welfare, privacy, and autonomy at every stage, ensuring that the dataset maintains a high degree of credibility, validity, and reliability.

Results and Discussion

Figure 3. T-test diagram
Source: Processed Data (2025)

In according of Ghozali & Fuad (2006), if P value < 0.05, then Ho (empirical data identical with research theory/model) is rejected, and if P value ≥ 0.05, then Ha (empirical data is different than theory/model) is not rejected. The data is analysed using α 0.05, the t-table value is 1.96. If t-test result value is higher than the critical t-table, which is higher than 1.96 means all variable relationships with measurable parameters have a significant effect. Based on the t-test result comparison with t-table, the result shown that all endogenous and exogenous variables have significant influence, and all measurable parameters have significant influence, and Ho is not rejected. The estimated size of inter-variable influence for SERV and LIST to brand equity and brand equity to customer equity is shown figure 3

Figure 4. T-test diagram (2)
Source: Processed Data (2025)

To measure the inter-variable influence, another t-test is done as shown in Figure 4, and the direct and indirect effects between variables are calculated as shown in Table 2. SERV and LIST, has direct and indirect influence. The size of the direct influence of SERV to brand equity is $(0.44 \times 0.44) = 0.19$ or 19%, while the indirect influence of SERV to brand equity through LIST is $(0.44 \times 0.51 \times 0.60) = 0.13$ or 13% (where SERV and LIST correlation value is 0.51), so the total SERV influence to brand equity is $(19\% + 13\%) = 32\%$. The size of lifestyle mix (LIST) direct influence to brand equity is $(0.60 \times 0.60) = 0.36$ or 36%, while the indirect influence of LIST on brand equity through SERV is $(0.60 \times 0.51 \times 0.44) = 0.13$ or 13%, so the LIST total influence to brand equity is $(36\% + 13\%) = 49\%$. Hence, the SERVLIST influence on brand equity is $(32\% + 49\%) = 81\%$. The lifestyle mix (LIST) influence on brand equity is stronger than the service mix (SERV). LIST influence on brand equity is higher at 49%, compared to LIST influence of 36% and the total SERVLIST influence on brand equity of 81%.

Table 2. Estimated Parameter of Inter-Variable Influence Size

Inter Variable Relationship	Influence rate
SERV → BRAND	32%
LIST → BRAND	49%
SERVLIST → BRAND	81%
BRAND → EQUITY	70%
SERVLIST → BRAND → EQUITY	LIST Dominant

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Further, the relationship of brand equity to customer equity in a simultaneous recursive way is a relational model that has a significant and positive influence, which is a direct relationship with the influence of $(0.84 \times 0.84) = 0.70$ or 70%. As mentioned in the research results (table 2), both SERV and LIST variables significantly influence brand equity. LIST (lifestyle mix) influences brand equity performance most dominantly compared to SERV (service mix), and brand equity has a significant direct influence on customer equity performance in full mediation. Brand equity is an endogenous variable on the hypothesis 1 (H-1) model that becomes an exogenous variable to customer equity on hypothesis 2 (H-2) (simultaneous recursive). The importance of individual lifestyle need fulfillment from the self-expression need dimension is that it can shape the customer perception of a brand, as shown in the study conducted by Catalin and Laurentiu (2014). It is important because it is the foundation of customer loyalty that will build future customer equity.

Findings

The focus of the beauty service marketing strategy for premium-class beauty salon service in order to increase brand equity performance should be on lifestyle mix (LIST) performance followed by attention to the need for beauty salon services to maintain high service mix (SERV) value for their customer. Although LIST has a more dominant influence (49%), SERV also has a significant influence of 32% on brand equity performance. Both variables equally need important attention. But based on previous studies done by Buttle (2009) customer demand is no longer on service mix (SERV) performance, but it is instead a lifestyle necessity. This is supported by the result of these hypothesis tests, which found that 81% of brand equity on premium beauty services is influenced by SERVLIST mix performance. This indicates that using the service mix (SERV) with the lifestyle mix (LIST) as an integrated SERVLIST marketing mix has a greater influence on brand equity. This research also has the advantage of using the LISA dimension model which is an approach to individual lifestyle needs modeling specific to the beauty service customer. The advantage of the individual approach compared to the use of social group lifestyle is that it is accurately closer to personal needs, as stated by Hawkins & Mothersbaug (2020) The H-1 and H-2 research model test results above show that to build strong brand equity, SERVLIST mix performance is an important beauty service mix, and it is a solution variable needed to be perceived as high quality. Maintaining a high level of perceived quality is important for a brand's reputation (Buttle, 2009; Yoo et al., 2000). At the same time, premium brand equity built through premium SERVLIST performance is needed to achieve high customer equity Thus, implementing lifestyle marketing while maintaining good service quality, should be expected as minimum standard of marketing strategy to meet customer demand in the beauty service industry. This is the reason the beauty services industry needs to adopt a lifestyle and services marketing

mix to maintain business sustainability in the long term. In the brand equity and customer equity relationship model of the beauty salon marketing service, customer equity is strongly influenced by the brand equity variable. The stronger the brand equity influence, the customer equity of any beauty salon service will become stronger accordingly. This relationship was proven by H3 result. Therefore, the full mediation model built for this research is suitable. By using the brand equity model as the intervening variable of the full mediation model, it can be said that without brand equity, it would be challenging to build customer equity in the beauty services industry. This result is also supported by previous research from Lemon et al. (2001) and Hellier et al (2003). The research result also provides a brand equity measurement model with a customer-based approach. The advantage of this model is customer characteristics that based on customer expectations for successful business long-term relationships. It also creates a paradigm to solve existing problems to maintain business sustainability in the beauty service industry. Customer equity can be built through creating value from the customer relationship) to accelerate and strengthen the cash flow to eventually reducing cash flow volatility and vulnerability of business sustainability (Kim et al., 2012; Srivastava et al., 1998; Widjaja, 2020).

Theoretical And Practical Implication

This study advances services marketing theory by reconceptualizing lifestyle from a background consumer characteristic into an operable and strategically integrated component of the marketing mix. Prior research has predominantly treated lifestyle as a segmentation variable or as an indirectly embedded element within experiential or service quality frameworks, thereby limiting its explanatory power in emotionally and symbolically driven service contexts (Joseph & Singh, 2013; Wirtz, 2020). By empirically validating the Lifestyle Marketing Mix (LIST) as a distinct construct alongside the traditional Service Marketing Mix (SERV), this research extends prevailing services marketing models by demonstrating that lifestyle-oriented marketing mechanisms exert a stronger influence on brand equity than conventional service attributes in premium beauty services. Furthermore, the study contributes to brand equity theory by establishing brand equity as a full mediating mechanism through which integrated marketing mix performance (SERVLIST) translates into customer equity, reinforcing brand equity's role as a central market-based asset in achieving long-term business sustainability (Aaker, 1991; Yoo et al., 2000; Kim et al., 2012). In doing so, the research provides a theoretically grounded explanation for why service firms operating in identity-expressive industries must move beyond service performance optimization toward lifestyle congruence as a strategic imperative, thereby extending the boundaries of service marketing mix theory and customer equity research.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that both the traditional service marketing mix and the lifestyle marketing mix play significant roles in shaping brand equity within the premium beauty services industry. Consistent with the proposed SERVLIST framework, the findings reveal that lifestyle-oriented marketing strategies exert a stronger influence on brand equity than conventional service mix elements. This result reflects the increasingly lifestyle-driven, emotionally expressive, and identity-oriented nature of beauty service consumption, particularly within premium market segments. Importantly, the study confirms that brand equity functions as a full mediating mechanism between integrated marketing mix performance and customer equity. This finding reinforces the strategic role of brand equity as a market-based asset that translates marketing effectiveness into long-term customer value and business sustainability. In the absence of strong brand equity, the capacity of service firms to accumulate customer equity remains constrained, even when service quality and lifestyle offerings are competently executed. By empirically validating lifestyle marketing mix dimensions as an integral component of service marketing strategy, this research extends existing theories in services marketing and brand equity. The findings demonstrate that lifestyle congruence is not merely an experiential enhancement but a core strategic driver of brand and customer equity formation in high-involvement service contexts. For practitioners, these results suggest that premium beauty salons must move beyond service performance optimization toward marketing strategies that genuinely resonate with consumers' lifestyles, emotional needs, and self-concepts. This study is subject to three principal limitations. First, the concentration of data within Jakarta's premium salon market, which may restrict generalizability across other regions and market segments. Second, the cross-sectional design, which constrains the ability to trace longitudinal shifts in lifestyle orientation and brand perception. Lastly,

the reliance on self-reported data, which introduces an inherent risk of response bias. Future research may address these limitations through longitudinal designs that examine how lifestyle marketing mix effectiveness and brand equity evolve under changing macroeconomic and sociocultural conditions, as well as comparative investigations across different service industries or between premium and mass-market segments to delineate the boundary conditions of the SERVLIST framework. Incorporating additional mediating or moderating variables, such as customer involvement, digital engagement, or cultural orientation, would further advance theoretical understanding of lifestyle marketing's influence on brand and customer equity formation. Extending the empirical scope beyond Indonesia to other emerging and developed markets would ultimately strengthen the cross-cultural validity and broader applicability of lifestyle marketing mix theory within the global services marketing literature.

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